

Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability, reuse and gaps for MNP-risk related tools

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1. What methods are you developing (or applying) for risk analysis/risk assessment?

(Decision trees to support development of) IATAs	PMCDs - Prospective multi criteria decision support system
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integrated approach to testing and assessment as structured, hypothesis-driven approach• Consideration of nano and microplastic and associated chemicals• Current focus: oral exposure (food contact materials)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Tool for early risk assessment of plastic applications, applicable in early developmental stages• Considers polymers, material fate, additives, adsorbed contaminants, etc.• Screening based on prospective risk indicators• Allows identification of risk minimized materials

2. What type of data are needed? - IATAs

- According to OECD, basically all available information on impact & interaction of a substance on organisms is gathered, integration of science based data, information and knowledge (e.g. phys.-chem. properties of NMP, appropriate test methods...)
- Hypothesis-driven -> data needs depend on hypothesis
- Integrating various toxicity testing approaches: in vitro, in in vivo, QSARs, AOPs....
- Specific case of oral exposure: transfer across GIT barrier, internal fate of NMP, biopersistence, internal fragmentation, release of chemicals (transformation products, additives...), suitable assays, trigger values (e.g. for size limits, amount of leached substances...)

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General	Specific for nano and microplastic / additives
<p>max/min values of a criteria</p> <p>Quality of data</p> <p>criteria weight and index values</p> <p>qualitative and/or quantitative criteria</p> <p>average values for each alternative</p> <p>Number of criteria</p> <p>normalized matrix</p>	<p>polymer type</p> <p>field of application</p> <p>life-cycle stage</p> <p>mass flow</p> <p>release factors</p> <p>transfer factors</p> <p>MNP in environmental compartments (air, soil, water)</p> <p>transition of MNP into air, food, etc.</p> <p>direct availability of MNP for humans</p> <p>uptake of MNP by humans (inhalation, ingestion, dermal)</p> <p>probability of resorption of MNP</p> <p>exposure probability to MNP</p> <p>uptake routes</p> <p>adsorbed contaminants</p> <p>physico-chemical properties</p> <p>additives</p>

3. What sources do you use to obtain the data?

- Data generated within the PlasticsFatE project: PC data, hazard data (mainly in vitro), data storage and exchange via Excel templates (EnanoMapper)
- data from previous and ongoing projects, e.g. Gracious, inaction with CUSP projects
- Scientific literature (different search engines)
- Others:
 - grey literature
 - guidance documents (e.g. <https://echa.europa.eu/mapping-exercise-plastic-additives-initiative>, <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/iata-integrated-approaches-to-testing-and-assessment.htm>; <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/testing/adverse-outcome-pathways-molecular-screening-and-toxicogenomics.htm>)

4. Are there any problems in collecting these data?

- General data gaps (relevant nanoplastics, broader range of polymer types, additive content...) e.g. only few data for LDPE, HDPE, EPS, SBR in comparison to PS
- Data bases for nano and microplastic PC and toxicity data: restricted availability
- Laborious search for data points: scientific literature, data quality (-> lecture by Anita)
- Methods are not available, e.g. characterisation, leaching, fragmentation of particles.....
- Data formats: e.g. no effect concentrations calculated, but those are required as input data; normalisation / weighting
- Independent publications reporting on opposing results (effect observed/effect not observed)

Summary

- 2 tools with different scope of risk analysis and data needs
- IATAs: hypothesis driven, variable data needs, consideration of respective test methods, broader range of information
- PMCDS: product-specific, designed to deal with data gaps & uncertainties, also qualitative data are considered
- several data gaps identified

Thank you for your attention

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